

THE EVALUATION OF ITALIAN TRANSLATION STUDIES

Xolmirzayeva Sevinch Sherzod qizi

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

A first-year student of the faculty Translation

sevinchkholmirzaeva@gmail.com

+998902973720

ABSTRACT. The field of Italian translation studies has undergone significant evolution, shaped by historical, cultural, and theoretical developments. This article provides an overview of the key milestones and trends that have characterized Italian translation studies, from its beginnings to its current state of interdisciplinary inquiry. Beginning with an exploration of early translation practices in Italy, influenced by classical rhetoric and humanism, the article traces the emergence of translation theory in the Italian Renaissance(XV-XVI centuries) and its subsequent evolution during the Enlightenment(second half of XVIII centuries) and Romantic periods(end of XVIII century). The nineteenth and twentieth centuries witnessed the consolidation of translation studies as a distinct academic discipline, marked by seminal contributions from Italian scholars such as Umberto Eco and Italo Calvino. The article also examines the impact of globalization, digital technologies, and postcolonial theory on contemporary Italian translation studies. By contextualizing the evolution of Italian translation studies within broader intellectual and socio-cultural frameworks, this article aims to provide insights into the rich heritage and ongoing developments in the field.

KEYWORDS. Historical development, cultural and theoretical development, Italian translation studies, translation practices, contributions, globalization.

Translation is a process that makes the meaning of messages, ideas, new concepts available from one language to another. It requires attention which makes it clearer, more accurate as well as understandable by considering cultural nuances. Translation, regarded as the channel facilitating the exchange of ideas, cultures, and

knowledge across linguistic boundaries, holds a pivotal role in the intricate web of human communication. This foundational concept of translation can be traced back to ancient civilizations, where early attempts were made to bridge linguistic gaps for the purpose of facilitating trade, diplomacy, and cultural exchange. The development of Italian studies serves as evidence of humanity's enduring pursuit of comprehension, cultural exchange, and intellectual exploration. This article sets out to explore the historical path and underlying principles that have influenced the discipline of language studies.

Italy is a well-known country for its rich cultural heritage as well as a literary tradition. From the Classical works of Dante Alighieri and Giovanni Boccaccio to the modern masterpieces of Italo Calvino, Elena Ferrante, Italian literature has become famous among readers worldwide, urging translators to render its essence into various languages and cultural contexts. The formal study of translation studies in Italy began to gain recognition and prominence in the twentieth century, particularly in the mid-20th century. While translation has been practiced and studied in Italy for centuries, it was during the 20th century that translation studies emerged as a distinct academic discipline within Italian universities[1]. The establishment of translation institutes, research centers and special academic programs has been the most essential achievement that they provided formal, detailed education as well as training to practice, and research in the evaluation of this field. Umberto Eco, Italo Calvino, and Cesare Segre, the most prominent Italian scholars, contributed to this field with their research works, publications that helped to advance the study of translation and its main essence within academic circles.

EARLY TRANSLATION PRACTICES IN ITALY

It was instrumental in facilitating cultural exchange, languages, and ideas as this country's geographical location at the crossroads of Europe. In fact, translations were crucial in transmitting knowledge from ancient civilizations such as Greek, Roman texts, into Italian. Moving to the Middle Ages, Italy was a center of scholars,

learning. Monasteries and universities were standouts in translating theological and scientific works from Latin and Greek into Italian language. In addition, Arabic influence (Middle Ages, particularly during the Islamic expansion into the Mediterranean region) has contributed to translation practices. Information in Greek, Latin, Arabic was later translated into Italian which has a valuable effect in terms of philosophical, literary knowledge. Later Italian translators like Niccolò Malermi, Giovanni Diodati, Giovanni Luzzi translated religious texts, especially biblical texts into Italian, paving the way for the development of the Italian literary language [2].

TRANSLATION IN THE ITALIAN RENAISSANCE PERIOD

During the Italian Renaissance, translation theory improved a lot as scholars grappled with questions of language, fidelity, style, and cultural adaptation. While translation theory during this period was not yet formalized into distinct schools or methodologies as we see in modern times, several key ideas and practices emerged that influenced translation practices and laid the groundwork for future theoretical developments. Leonardo Bruni (1370-1444), Marsilio Ficino (1433-1499), and Lorenzo Valla (1407-1457), humanist scholars translated classical texts into the vernacular languages [3]. They were translators who believed that by making ancient knowledge accessible to people with the help of translation, later that audience could contribute to the advancements of learning and civilization. Translators in the Renaissance period often used literal translation techniques to convey the author's inner intention for writing the masterpiece as accurately as possible to capture the essence of the original work. Renaissance translators were not accepted as transcribers of texts but as creative people between cultures, as they often left their mark on the translated texts. Also, there were notable translations that shaped cultural and intellectual developments. The Greek epics "Iliad" and "Odyssey" were translated into Italian by Matteo Maria Boiardo, Francesco Griffolini who helped to make the ancient Greek epics for Italians [4]. "Plato's Dialogues" was another work

that came up during the Renaissance period by a leading figure of this period's humanism, Marsilio Ficino.

TRANSLATION STUDIES IN THE ENLIGHTENMENT AND ROMANTIC PERIODS

The Enlightenment period (the intellectual and cultural movement that occurred during the 18th century) was a period in which the focus was directed to emphasize reason, rationality, and the dissemination of knowledge in translation studies. Works during that period were often seen as a means to spread scientific, philosophical, and political ideas across borders. Italian translators, in order to make the rich intellectual heritage accessible to Italian readers, actively engaged in works in French, English, and German. For example, scientific literature by figures Newton, Francis Bacon was translated to introduce Italians to the latest developments in mathematics, physics. Cesare Beccaria's influential work which was written in 1764, "On Crimes and Punishments" was another translated outcome by Gaetano Filangieri, contributing to the discourse on legal reform and human rights during the Enlightenment period [5]. Moving to Political Literature, translations of John Locke's "Two Treatises of Government" and Jean-Jacques Rousseau's "The Social Contract" by Filippo Venuti influenced Italian debates on this sphere [6].

The main aspects of the Romantic period (a cultural, artistic, and literary movement that emerged in the late 18th century and reached its peak in the first half of the 19th century) translation studies were linked to emotion, imagination, and national identity. One of the most noteworthy figures in this field was Ugolo Foscolo (1778-1827), who was not only a poet or writer but a translator with his translations describing literary criticism and helped shape the Italian literary scene of his time. Furthermore, the Romantic period underwent the emergence of translation as a scholarly discipline as scholars began to analyze the techniques, strategies, and their

role in forming literary reception, by discussing the challenges of capturing the meaning of foreign texts while adapting to the Italian language in a cultural context.

CONTEMPORARY ITALIAN TRANSLATION STUDIES

The influence of Globalization, digital technologies, and postcolonial theory is worth noting when we talk about the condition of these studies in this modernized era. Globalization has profoundly impacted the field of translation in Italy by amplifying the demand for translation services across a wide array of sectors including business, diplomacy, media, and academia [7]. In Italy, this has meant a growing need for translators who can facilitate communication between Italian speakers and people from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds by navigating issues of cultural sensitivity and intercultural communication in terms of ensuring cross-cultural exchange. Moreover, digital developments have increased efficiency by implying platforms such as DeepL, SDL Trados, and memoQ by providing a range of versions of meanings and forms. Although the benefits are countless, translation studies should take into consideration the accuracy, quality control, and surely the preservation of linguistic, cultural nuances by estimating the output of machine translation systems, maintaining fidelity to the source.

Translation studies as well as works have witnessed such kinds of steps. Translators have played a significant role in shaping the way of thinking and being aware of further developments that have been implemented outside of Italy. The evaluation of Italian translation studies discloses a dynamic field that continues to change in response to different sorts of improvements. The commitment to interdisciplinary inquiry of this country's translation enhancements highlights the interplay between language, power, and identity. Moreover, the integration of digital technologies reshaped the landscape of this field by offering new possibilities for efficiency, collaboration, also posing challenges related to linguistic accuracy, the preservation of cultural nuances.

REFERENCES:

1. Michael Caesar, Peter Hainsworth. (1996). Translation in Modern Italy: A Cultural History.
2. Michael Caesar. (2016). Translation and the Making of Modern Italian Literature. https://books.google.co.uz/books?id=PMDt-SQsAv4C&printsec=frontcover&source=gbs_ge_summary_r&cad=0#v=onepage&q&f=false
3. Kenneth R. Barlett. (2011). The Civilization of the Italian Renaissance: Sourcebook. https://www.google.co.uz/books/edition/The_Civilization_of_the_Italian_Renaissance/8duCpxbqUp4C?hl=en&gbpv=0
4. Cronin, M. (2013). Translation in the digital age. Routledge. https://www.google.co.uz/books/edition/Translation_in_the_Digital_Age/BzaBT7jYurMC?hl=en&gbpv=0
5. O'Hagan, M., & Ashworth, D. (2002). Translation-mediated communication in a digital world: Facing the challenges of globalization and localization. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters.
6. Snell-Hornby, M. (2006). The turns of translation studies: New paradigms or shifting viewpoints? John Benjamins Publishing Company.
7. Gaetano Filangieri, John B., (2010). Cesare Beccaria and Eighteenth-century Italian Enlightenment(57-58pp). The John Hopkins University Press.